

HOW TRANSFORMATIONAL STYLE AND INTERNAL SERVICE QUALITY IMPACT ON THE JOB SATISFACTION OF EMPLOYEES AT HOSPITAL

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the impact of *Transformational Leadership style* and *Internal Service Quality on Job Satisfaction* in Hospital. This is a quantitative study that uses a cross-sectional method. The Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ-5X) is used to measure the leadership style variable, The ISQ instrument from SERVQUAL that modified to ensure internal service quality, and Job Satisfaction was measured by a questionnaire that has been developed and validated for health workers in healthcare institutions. Data was collected from 243 employees of the Daya General Hospital Makassar who were selected by random quota sampling and then analyzed using the Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The results show that the transformational leadership style has a positively significant effect on job satisfaction (t statistic 3.679; $p < 0.000$; β coefficient 0.329). *Internal service quality* style has a positively significant effect on *job dissatisfaction* (t statistic 5.446; $p < 0.000$; β coefficient 0.473). Transformational leadership style has a positively significant effect on internal service quality (t statistic 33.832; $p < 0.000$; β coefficient 0.805). Transformational leadership style has more significant effect on job satisfaction Trough internal service quality (t statistic 5,217; $p < 0,000$; β coefficient 0.380). The results show that the transformational leadership style is the most effective leadership style among the three leadership styles that were analyzed. Transformational leadership style has a positively significant effect on job satisfaction (t statistic 3.679; $p < 0.000$; β coefficient 0.329). *Internal service quality* style has a positively significant effect on *job dissatisfaction* (t statistic 5.446; $p < 0.000$; β coefficient 0.473). Transformational leadership style has a positively significant effect on internal service quality (t statistic 33.832; $p < 0.000$; β coefficient 0.805). Transformational leadership style has more significant effect on job satisfaction Trough internal service quality (t statistic 5,217; $p < 0,000$; β coefficient 0.380).

Keywords : Leadership Style, Internal Service Quality, Job Satisfaction, Healthcare System, Patient Safety, Service Quality

INTRODUCTION

Hospitals are part of a healthcare system that aims to improve public health and are required to constantly improve the performance of their employees to improve the quality of health services and patient safety while always trying to avoid increasing hospital operating costs [1]. Data from the Central Statistics Agency in 2020 states that the growth of hospitals in Indonesia is increasing, reaching 2,423 public and private hospitals, and 536 special hospitals, which shows the efforts of the government and the private sector to answer the demands of public health service coverage.

The development of technology that changes the world very quickly is the next challenge for hospitals today. Health technology and information systems are becoming a trend and always have the latest updates and become the competitiveness and selling points of hospitals that offer convenience and speed of service access to hospital customers. Rapid changes in healthcare highlight the importance of the role of healthcare organization leaders so that organizations have new skills to respond to fierce market competition. Organizations need leaders who demonstrate modern leadership characteristics to use digital technology, adapt to new skills and improve efficiency [2].

The quality and existence of leadership determine the success or failure of the organization. Leadership style becomes the standard of behavior of a leader to influence the behavior of others [3]. Healthcare leadership requires skills, abilities, behaviors, and knowledge to achieve improved quality of service products. The responsibilities of healthcare leadership include designing effective health policies and programs, ensuring the organization meets established medical and safety standards, and guiding and coordinating the medical and non-medical personnel engaged in it. The homework of healthcare leaders is to strengthen organizational management, health technology, and most importantly human resources [4]. Several studies found a significant impact of leadership style on job satisfaction, performance, commitment, and organizational culture [5]; [6]; [7]; [8].

One aspect of strengthening organizational managerial that can have an impact on employee satisfaction is through improving and enhancing services to internal hospital staff. Employees play a dual role as service providers for external customers but are also internal customers. Internal service quality (ISQ) is considered one of the main factors that affect employee loyalty, job satisfaction, and organizational productivity [9]; [10]; [11].

The ISQ system is considered an integral part of a consumer-oriented organization. The ISQ system focuses on providing a higher level of internal services by meeting the needs and satisfaction of employees as internal customers. The level of employee job satisfaction explains how the employee views his job, whether he is willing to work in the organization, and the extent to which the job is associated with positive and negative aspects [9].

Internal service quality is needed to achieve superior external service quality, therefore service providers, in this case organizational leaders, need to understand, influence, and directly drive efforts to improve the quality and satisfaction of human resources in service organizations [12].

Found in their research that different leadership styles affect internal service quality, innovation behavior, work standardization, and organizational service culture.

Participative and transformational leadership styles were shown to have a positive influence on internal service quality through various means [5]; [13]; [14]; [15].

Internal service quality (ISQ) is considered as one of the main drivers of employee loyalty, job satisfaction, and organizational productivity [10]; [11]. Therefore, an ISQ management system is considered integral to consumer-oriented organizations. It is focused on higher internal services through internal consumer satisfaction needs. Poor ISQ levels can severely undermine employee organizational commitment [11]. Therefore, researchers are interested in seeing how the influence of leadership style involves improving/managing internal service quality to increase hospital employee job satisfaction.

RESEARCH METHOD

Data collection, samples and measurements

The type of research used in this research is quantitative research with design *cross sectional*. This research was carried out at Daya General Hospital, Makassar, from November to December 2023. The population in this study were employees at Daya General Hospital, Makassar. Sampling for this research was carried out using techniques *simple random sampling* using the Slovin formula with a margin of error 5%, so that the number of samples obtained was 243 employees at Daya General Hospital, Makassar. Variable measurement uses Likert scale questionnaires and interviews, namely exogenous variables (*leadership style* and *internal service quality*), endogenous variables (*job satisfaction*).

Statistical Analysis

The data processing and analysis techniques used in this research use *Structural Equation Modeling* (SEM) SmartPLS. SEM is a multivariate statistical analysis method developed from regression and path analysis. The use of SEMPLS in this study is because three activities can be carried out simultaneously, namely checking the validity and reliability of the instrument (confirmatory factor analysis), testing the relationship model between variables (path analysis), and obtaining a model suitable for prediction (structural model analysis and regression analysis). Univariate and multivariate analyzes were carried out. Univariate analysis analyzes the existing variables descriptively by calculating the frequency distribution and proportions to determine the characteristics of the research subjects. In the multivariate analysis used is path analysis (*Path analysis*). Path analysis is an analytical technique used to analyze the influence/ causal relationship between variables.

RESULTS

Univariate Analysis

Univariate analysis is used to analyze a variable or a single data that is respondent's characteristics and a description of the respondent's perception of the research variables.

Table 1: Characteristics of Respondents Daya General Hospital Makassar

Respondent Characteristics		Amount	
		Height	
		n	%
Gender	Man	26	10.7
	Woman	217	89.3
Age	20-35 Years	58	23.9
	36-45 Years	136	56.0
	>45 Years	49	20.2
Work unit	Hospital Directors and Management	69	28.4
	Inpatient Installation	62	25.5
	Outpatient Installation	27	11.1
	Emergency Installation	16	6.58
	Central Surgical Installation	9	3.7
	Pharmaceutical Installation	12	4.9
	Nutrition Installation	16	6.58
	Laboratory Instalation	12	4.9
	Radiology Instalation	5	2.1
	Other Supporting Installations	15	6.2
Length of Work	1-10 Years	95	39.1
	11-20 Years	130	53.5
	21-30 Years	16	6.6
	31-40 Years	2	0.8
Working Hours	20-39 Hours a Week	99	40,7
	≥40 Hours a Week	115	68.5
Employment Status	Government employee	144	59.3
	Contract Worker	93	38.3
	Volunteer	6	2.5
Level of education	D3/ Equivalent	28	16.7
	DIV/ S1	82	48.8
	S2	5	3.0
	S3	53	31.5

Based on table 1 above, it shows that the majority of respondents are female as many as 217 respondents (89.3%) while male gender is 17 respondents (10.1%). The most respondents were in the age group of 36-45 years, which was 136 respondents (50%). The most respondents for work units is inpatient installation in 62 respondents (25.5%). For length of work was 11-20 years as many as 130 respondents (53.5%). The most respondents' for working hours were ≥40 hours a week as many as 115 respondents (68.5%). The highest respondent for employee status was ASN as many as 144 respondents (59.3%). The most respondent for level of education was DIV / S1 education as many as 152 respondents (62.6%).

Tabel 2: Description of Leadership Style Variables in Daya General Hospital Makassar

Dimension	Height	
	n	%
Transformational Leadership Style	200	82,3
Transactional Leadership Style	189	77,8
Laissez Faire Leadership Style	10	4,1

In Table 2, it can be seen that the Leadership Style variable for transformational leadership types has the highest achievement in the high category of 82.3% (200 respondents), the transactional leadership type category in the high category of 77.8% (189 respondents) and the Laissez Faire leadership type is in the lowest achievement in the high category of 4.1% (10 respondents). Transformational leadership style is then chosen to be a variable that will be tested for its effect on job satisfaction and internal service quality.

Table 3: Description of Research Variables Daya General Hospital Makassar

Variable	Height		Middle		Low	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
<i>Leadership Style</i>	179	73,7	63	25,9	1	0,4
<i>Internal Service Quality</i>	191	78,6	52	21,4	0	0,0
<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	183	75,3	56	23,0	4	1,6

Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents to the variables of this study obtained results, namely; Leadership Style with a high category of 66.1% (111 respondents), Internal Service Quality with a high category of 78.6% (191 respondents), and Job Satisfaction with a high category of 75.3% (183 respondents).

Multivariate Analysis

Multivariate analysis was used to see whether there is a direct or indirect influence between variables *leadership style and internal service quality* to variable *job satisfaction* through *burnout*. The method used is SEM PLS analysis with the support of Smartpls 4 software. SEM PLS carries out a two-step analysis, the first step is testing the measurement theory to confirm the reliability and validity of the measurement models and the second step is to test the structural theory.

Step I Measurement Model

The measurement models (also referred to as the outer models in PLS-SEM) of the constructs that display the relationships between the constructs and the indicator variables (rectangles) [16].

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is a multivariate statistical procedure that is used to test how well the measured variables represent the number of constructs. In (Hair Jr et al., 2021) CFA consists of *loading factor* $\geq 0,70$, *composite reliability dan cronbach's alpha* $\geq 0,70$, *average variance extracted (AVE)* $\geq 0,70$ as well *discriminant validity heterotrait monotrait ratio* (HTMT) below 0.90.

The loading factor value shows the correlation between the indicator and its construct. Indicators with low loading values indicate that the indicator does not work in the measurement model. The extent to which a variable or set of variables is consistent in terms of what it wants to assess is referred to as indicator dependence. Mark loading factor or outer loading greater than 0.7 is said to be valid [17].

Table 4: Loading Factor or Outer Loading Values

	Transformational Leadership Style	Internal Service Quality	Job Satisfaction
Idealized Influence Attribute	0,869		
Idealized Influence Behaviour	0,791		
Individualized Consideration	0,853		
Inspirational Motivation	0,893		
Intellectual Stimulation	0,779		
Assurance		0,923	
Empathy		0,957	
Reliable		0,967	
Responsible		0,896	
Tangible		0,895	
Communication			0,858
Empowerment Participation			0,904
Flexibility of Working Hours			0,816
Leadership			0,884
Reward Recognition			0,811
Teamwork			0,924
Training Development			0,904
Working Condition			0,800

From the results of data processing with SmartPLS shown in Table 4, all indicators for each variable in this study have a value *loading factor* or *outer loading* which is greater than 0.70 and is said to be valid. This shows that variable indicators that have a loading factor value greater than 0.70 have a high level of validity, so they meet *convergent validity*.

Cronbach Alpha and *Composite Reliability* values are used to assess the internal consistency reliability of each variable. A latent variable is declared reliable if *composite reliability* and *cronbach's alpha* has value $\geq 0,70$, then the construct is declared reliable [17].

Table 5: Composite Reliability

	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
Transformational Leadership Style	0,922	0,894
Internal Service Quality	0,969	0,960
Job Satisfaction	0,959	0,951

From the SmartPLS output results in Table 5 above, it shows that the value *Conbach's Alpha* and *Composite Reliability* each variable has met the standard, namely above 0.70. With the resulting value, it shows that each variable is above the value of 0.70. This shows that the reliability of the research is acceptable because it exceeds the limit the minimum value that has been required. Also, value *Composite Reliability* is also higher than the value *Cronbach's Alpha*. This indicates that all research variables have met the requirements regarding appropriate reliability criteria as a basis for SEM research which can be analyzed using SmartPLS.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE tests the validity of the construct can be done by paying attention to whether or not the correlation between the construct and the indicators forming the construct is strong, as well as a weak relationship with other constructs [17]. An AVE of ≥ 0.50 indicates that the construct explains more than half of the variance in the indicator. Discriminant validity represents the extent to which the

construct is empirically different from other constructs or in other words the construct measures what it is intended to measure.

Table 6: Composite Reliability

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Transformational Leadership Style	0,703
Job Satisfaction	0,746
Internal Service Quality	0,862

Table 6 above shows that all variables have met the specified AVE criteria, namely with a value of ≥ 0.5 . This shows that *Test Convergent Validity* is acceptable.

Discriminant validity heterotrait monotrait ratio (HTMT) is the average value of all indicator correlations across constructs measuring different constructs (i.e., heterotrait-heteromethod correlation) relative to the (geometric) average value of the average correlation of indicators measuring the same construct. According to [17], *valuediscriminant validity heterotrait monotrait ratio* (HTMT) should be ≤ 0.90 . When the construct has a HTMT value ≥ 0.90 carried out bootstrap test.

Table 7: Discriminant Validity Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	Transformational Leadership Style	Job Satisfaction	Internal Service Quality
Transformational Leadership Style			
Job Satisfaction	0,734		
Internal Service Quality	0,849	0,748	

Table 7 shows the values *discriminant validity heterotrait monotrait ratio* (HTMT) above is less than 0.90, so it can be said that there is a correlation between variables. Thus it can be said that the research model is formed from three variables, namely *transformational leadership style, internal service quality and job satisfaction*.

Testing the structural model/inner model is related to testing the hypothesis of the influence between research variables. The inner model is a structural model used to predict causal relationships (cause-effect relationships) between latent variables or variables that cannot be measured directly. The Inner Model in PLS is evaluated using coefficient values *path* (path that describes the strength of the relationship between variables) to test the significance between variables in the inner model (structural model).

Table 8: Structural model: Hypothesis test results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Transformational Leadership Style → Job Satisfaction	0,329	0,324	0,089	3,679	0,000
Internal Service Quality → Job Satisfaction	0,473	0,478	0,087	5,446	0,000
Transformational Leadership Style → Internal Service Quality	0,805	0,806	0,024	33,832	0,000

Based on Table 8 above, it reflects *path coefficients* which is the result of direct influence testing (*direct effect*). The table above shows that *transformational leadership style* influence on *job satisfaction* with t statistics 3.679 ($p < 0.000$). *Internal*

service quality influence on job satisfaction with t statistics 5.446 ($p < 0.000$). Transformational leadership style influence on internal service quality with t statistics 33.823 ($p < 0.000$).

Figure 1: Results Structural model

DISCUSSION

The aim of this research is to determine influence of leadership style and internal service quality variables on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is intended as an emotional perception that naturally arises from employees about the job or workplace and other factors that are assessed based on experience and achievements possessed. Several studies have shown that increasing job satisfaction becomes a key goal in the face of challenges related to the achievement and maintenance of quality standards, ensuring patient satisfaction and staff retention [18]; [19].

This study first determined the most dominant type of leadership style applied at Daya General Hospital, Makassar. The results obtained show that transformational leadership types has the highest achievement in the high category of 82.3% (200 respondents), than the transactional leadership type and the Laissez Faire leadership type. Transformational leadership style is then chosen to be a variable that will be tested for its effect on internal service quality and job satisfaction. Transformational leadership shows how leaders motivate and inspire their subordinates to unleash higher potential. Leaders who adopt a transformational leadership style encourage subordinates to be innovative and creative, thus finding new ways of solving complex problems. Transformational leaders bring new things, new inspiration, and new behaviors to organizations [20]; [21].

Based on the results of research conducted on employees at the Daya General Hospital Makassar, shows that transformational leadership style have an positive significant effect on job satisfaction. The results appear to be in line with research in the healthcare sector conducted by several studies that have explored the relationship

between transformational leadership and job satisfaction in the healthcare industry. Among them are [22], research in Turkey and another study in Malaysia [23] a, found that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and innovative behavior in nurses in hospitals. The results of the study by [20], also discuss the relationship between transformational leadership styles and job satisfaction in healthcare units, suggesting that strengthening employee positions is necessary to increase job satisfaction.

Similar to external service quality, internal service quality (ISQ) can be defined as the quality of service or perceived satisfaction regarding the services offered by different departments and the people working in these departments to other departments and people working within the organization. Overall, maintaining job satisfaction among hospital employees is important to hospital success, as motivated and productive employees can contribute greatly to the overall quality of services provided to external customers [10]; [24]; [25]; [26].

The purpose of this research is to see how internal service quality influence job satisfaction. Based on the test results, it shows that the internal service quality variable has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with an estimate of 0.473, meaning that if the internal service quality variable increases by one unit, then job satisfaction increases by 47%.

The quality of internal services can have a significant impact on job satisfaction in the healthcare sector. The results of this study are in line with several studies on internal service quality on job satisfaction, including the results obtained in this study also in accordance with research [27] conducted on 441 medical personnel in hospitals in Greece. The same results were also found by previous [9]; [28]; [25] who found that Internal Service Quality has a positive impact on Job Satisfaction.

Overall, the relationship between internal service quality and job satisfaction in healthcare can be complex and may depend on a variety of factors such as specific healthcare organization and cultural context. The results of this study are not in line with research [29] of 104 nurses at RSI Surabaya, finding that the quality of internal services does not have a significant effect on nurses' job satisfaction, but aspects of reward and recognition can have an almost significant effect on nurses' job satisfaction.

The third purpose of this study is to see the influence of leadership style on the internal service quality of employees of Daya General Hospitas, Makassar. The results show that transformational leadership variables positively significant influence on internal service quality. The results of this study are in line with previous research [30]; [31] on hotel employees in Taiwan, where transformational and transactional leadership styles have a positive correlation with internal service quality. Transformational leadership exerts the greatest influence on the quality of internal services. The level of internal service quality for internal customers will be higher if employees perceive that the hotel has a clear division of responsibilities, a good organizational structure, and performs supervisory functions. The supervisor provides a clear vision and mission, takes advantage of his influence to change internal attitudes, and encourages subordinates to put aside personal interests to make joint efforts for the benefit of the hotel. The results show that transformational leadership variables positively and significantly influence internal service quality.

Transformational leadership influences the behavior of employees to provide service and support to their colleagues [30]. found that transactional leadership has a positive effect on employees helping their colleagues and working together to achieve organizational or departmental goals.

The fourth objective of this study was to find the right path between the three variables, it was found that there was a visible form of mediation between the three variables, where internal service quality can be a mediator or intervening variable between the independent variable transformational leadership style and the dependent variable job satisfaction. The mediation test was conducted to see how strong the mediating effect of the internal service quality variable was in this study. The mediation test results reveal that the Internal Service Quality variable is able to mediate the Transformational Leadership Style variable on Job Satisfaction as the dependent variable with a statistical t value of 5.217 and a p value of 0.000. Mediating or intervening variables are defined as variables that are located between the independent and dependent variables which affect the relationship between the independent variables into an indirect relationship that affects the change or emergence of the dependent variable [32].

The results of this study are a novelty of previous studies where researchers have not found previous research that draws the influence of leadership style with internal service quality mediation on job satisfaction. Through this study, it was found that the internal service quality variable was able to mediate the transformational leadership style variable to produce a positive and significant effect on the job satisfaction variable.

Their study explored topics related to the health sector including the performance-excellence model, internal satisfaction, external satisfaction, and the model of connecting internal and external satisfaction and then combining them in a conceptual model with the name "Service Excellence Chain (SEC)" [33].

In the Service Excellence Chain model "Leadership" is an important driver because it positively influences all organizational enablers ("people", "partnerships and resources" and "processes"). "People", "partnerships and resources" contribute to "process" which influences "product". On the other hand, the "product" construct impacts "employee satisfaction". This model indirectly explains the involvement of leadership style variables in influencing internal service quality as a mediator that will affect job satisfaction [33].

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this research that transformational leadership style and internal service quality on job satisfaction. Transformational leadership style affects internal service quality and also transformational leadership style affects employees' job satisfaction through internal quality service in hospitals. Therefore, hospital leaders should motivate themselves to learn and apply transformational styles at every level of management in the hospital organization. The transformational leadership style also can be one of the considerations for hospital owners include top level management, to always be selective in choosing or appointing leaders at middle and low level management of the hospital organization. Leadership skills of healthcare leaders are needed; leaders' age and tenure need to be further measured to improve job satisfaction among healthcare workers. The transformational leadership style is

involved in improving the quality of internal hospital services through several forms of improving internal service quality in the form of reformulating service standards, fostering a culture of service excellence, providing supporting resources, motivating and stimulating enthusiastic employees to work according to and even exceeding the established internal service standards.

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